

THE USE OF MICROSOFT TEAMS IN LEARNING ENGLISH FOR SECONDARY LEVEL: TEACHERS' AND STUDENTS' VIEWS

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ABSTRACT

Education in Indonesia has undergone a change from face-to-face learning in class to online learning due to the spread of the coronavirus (COVID-19). To support the online learning practices, SMP Brawijaya Smart School utilizes Microsoft Teams as the platform especially for online English learning. This study aims to find out teachers' and students' perception in using Microsoft Teams in learning English. The sample of this study was 2 English teachers' and 180 students from 8th and 9th grades. To reach the aim of the study, quantitative research with survey design was used, with questionnaire to collect the data was conducted, and with SPSS to analyze the quantitative data was used. The results showed that teachers and students at SMP Brawijaya Smarts School had a positive perception of using Microsoft Teams in learning English. Teachers' and students also found out that learning English through Microsoft Teams was easy to be used because Microsoft Teams provided many features that the teachers and students can access in one platform. In another say, Microsoft Teams is the one-stop platform for learning.

KEYWORDS

Microsoft Teams, perception, online English learning

INTRODUCTION

The Indonesian government is taking the necessary actions to pay close attention to report about the World Health Organization (WHO) related to the worldwide COVID-19 outbreak since the virus was first discovered in Wuhan, South China, in November 2019. The virus quickly orbited the globe and has at last follow up on each mainland except for Antarctica (Chakraborty & Maity, 2020). Since March 2020, education in Indonesia has undergone a change from face-to-face learning in class to online learning due to the spread of the coronavirus (COVID-19). The Indonesia Minister of Education and Culture issued an education policy in the emergency period of the spread of COVID-19 with the teaching and learning process carried out from home through e-learning platforms (Kemdikbud, 2020). The use of e-learning platforms in online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic is urgently needed. Moreover, in learning English, the teacher must use an e-learning platform that can cover four skills in learning English.

In a COVID-19 pandemic situation, EFL teachers have implemented online learning through various activities, from checking student attendance, giving assignments to assigning scores through e-learning platforms (Atmojo & Nugroho, 2020). ELF teachers have difficulty in online learning, such as providing learning materials and assessment, getting trouble into an internet connection, further, and teachers find difficulties in students' low motivation in the discussion (Atmojo & Nugroho, 2020). Therefore, using a suitable platform is very important in learning English.

The use of the platform has concentrated on how the teachers integrate technology in teaching and learning English to reach students and teach them at home. There are many synchronous and asynchronous platforms that can help teachers to teach English during pandemic COVID-19.

According to Hrastinski (2008), a synchronous platform is a platform that is supported by video conferences and chat media. Teachers and students can answer and ask questions in real-time. Zoom, Google Meet, Skype are examples of synchronous platforms. The asynchronous platform is facilitated by media such as e-mail and discussion boards, which supports online learning between teachers and students even when students cannot be online simultaneously (Hrastinski, 2008). Examples of asynchronous platforms are Google Classroom, WhatsApp, and Quipper. One of the platforms effectively used for online learning in the COVID-19 pandemic situation is Microsoft Teams.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, SMP Brawijaya Smart School, all teaching and learning activities are online from home using a platform. Learning activities are carried out by video conferencing to explain the material for 30 minutes and giving assignments to students is carried out asynchronously. The teacher offers tasks based on the material explained through video conference and collected according to the given time limit. At SMP Brawijaya Smart School, teachers use a platform that functions as synchronous and asynchronous, namely Microsoft Teams.

Microsoft Teams is a synchronous and asynchronous platform with around 13 million users (Spataro, 2019). It is a cloud application that brings conversation, video meetings, sharing a file, and other applications in Microsoft in one application (Koenigsbauer, 2020). By Microsoft teams, teachers and students can communicate in many ways. They can use real-time text chat, video call, voice, fun emojis, gifts, and stickers. Teachers can also easily set up assignments within teams. To access it, teachers and students just need to install Microsoft Teams in the Apps store on their phones or laptops to access it. Microsoft Teams presents better features than other platforms. The advantages of Microsoft Teams are unlimited call duration, the use of Microsoft Teams is integrated with Office 365 such as Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel, and Microsoft PowerPoint. Unlike Zoom and Google Meet platforms, Microsoft Teams users are few and rarely use it. However, since the COVID-19 pandemic, Microsoft Teams users have reached 115 million users.

Rojabi (2020) argues that the use of Microsoft Teams in learning English effectively affects students' learning environment and supports their interaction. Other research from students at the university level in Turkey and Jordan also found that Microsoft teams are effectively on evaluation process took much less time, and efficiency and the use of Microsoft teams is convenient, can be accessed from anywhere (Alabay, 2018; Rababah, 2020). This research will investigate teachers' and students' perceptions of using Microsoft teams in learning English at SMP Brawijaya Smart School. It is necessary to conduct since the pandemic of COVID-19 SMP Brawijaya Smart School has been using Microsoft Teams to learn English. The findings of this research are expected to be beneficial for the teachers and students. It is expected to know the effectiveness of using Microsoft Teams in learning English. And this research is also likely to know the advantages and disadvantages of using Microsoft Teams.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Online English Learning

During the COVID 19 pandemic, almost all schools in Indonesia carried out online lessons to reduce transmission. Online learning is a teaching and learning process that utilizes the internet and digital technology to convey material. According to Atmojo & Nugroho (2020), online learning is a teaching and learning activity in a subject that is delivered by internet networks. Furthermore, online learning uses the internet and other relevant technology to construct teaching material, provide instruction, and manage a program (Fry, 2001 cited in Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020). In online

English learning, teachers and students use gadgets or laptops to learn online. Teachers use several platforms to access on gadgets or laptops, including WhatsApp, Google Classroom, Google Forms, Google Meet, Zoom, and Moodle.

In SMP Bawijaya Smart School, since the COVID-19 pandemic have been used Microsoft Teams as the platform for online English learning. Microsoft Teams is a synchronous and asynchronous platform that brings together conversations, video conferencing, and other Microsoft applications in one place. Teachers can use Microsoft Teams for face-to-face or synchronous online learning, such as explaining the material. Teachers can also upload course material that students can view in the file features in Microsoft Teams. In Microsoft Teams, there is an assignment feature; in this feature, teachers can upload assignments and set a time limit for students to submit assignments. Teachers can also provide grades immediately and correct student assignments from the files they collect. Microsoft Teams is a simple, easy-to-use platform for online learning for teachers and students.

Microsoft Teams

Microsoft Teams was first launched in November 2016 at an event in New York City. Microsoft Teams is accessible in 181 countries and 18 languages and is officially available in the first half of 2017. Microsoft Team is a technological hub that brings conversation, meetings, files, and apps together in one application (Microsoft, 2021). Microsoft Teams also gives better features like other platforms that cover chat room, collaborative discussion, and video conferencing (Buchal & Songsore, 2019; Henderson et al., 2020; Hubbard & Bailey, 2018; Ilag, 2020; McVey et al., 2019; Tsai, 2018, cited in Rojabi, 2020). For education, Microsoft Teams has collaborated with Microsoft 365, such as Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel, Microsoft PowerPoint, Microsoft Outlook, OneNote, and OneDrive. Furthermore, Microsoft Teams for education consists of seven features: activity, chat, teams, assignment, calendar, calls, and file. The activity features contain chats, teams, assignments, calendars, and files. Chat features contain individual chats with students, and for teams features, contains a list of Teams or classes.

Microsoft Teams in Online Learning

Online learning with Microsoft Teams has been widely used at various levels of education. One of the universities that used Microsoft Teams as a platform in online learning is the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education (FKIP) Nusa Nipa University (UNIPA). They have used Microsoft Teams since the COVID-19 spread. Wea & Dua Kuki (2021) stated that online learning using Microsoft Teams made students enthusiastic in preparing for the lesson. Students were allowed to build communication and interaction with lectures and classmates using this platform. The researcher also added that students have difficulty with bad internet connections during online learning using Microsoft Teams. Apart from the difficulty, the students expected that the online learning process would keep using Microsoft Teams (Wea & Dua Kuki, 2021).

At the American College of Cardiology, The Brigham and Women's Hospital Fellowship also used Microsoft Teams as a platform for online learning. According to Almarzooq et al., (2020), before the COVID-19 pandemic, the main learning was a Friday morning conference followed by a cardiology fellow. However, it has changed into online conferences using Microsoft Teams since the pandemic. They used virtual meetings, chats for ongoing discussion or messaging to individuals or teams, screen share, and recorded for fellows to review at their time off. The researcher added the challenge of this platform lies in faculties of availability to understand how to use this technology. In fact, in the post-COVID-19, they trust that medical training programs would get high profit from using this virtual learning platform (Almarzooq et al., 2020).

Online learning with Microsoft Teams is also found in language learning. At the University of Education, the University of Da Nang used Microsoft Teams for online teaching and learning in English courses during the COVID-19 pandemic. According to Yen & Nhi (2021), Microsoft Teams gives advantages in online teaching. Students at the University of Da Nang can re-watch the lecture video. They can easily download the video. The students also can easily communicate with the teachers and classmates. They used chat features and interacted with them. Besides the benefit of using Microsoft Teams in online teaching, the researcher also found the frequently encountered problems. The teachers and students get into difficulty with the internet connection. Sometimes they cannot log in, or the audio or video quality is bad. The use of Microsoft Teams has many efforts from teachers. They spend lots of time preparing lessons, and another challenge for teachers is checking the students' attendance in online classes (Yen & Nhi, 2021).

Perception

Perception can be defined as an individual's opinion about something. According to Campbell (1967, cited in Ahen, 2009), perception is defined as being observed and what is said about it. The researcher also said that perception would form an impression about someone or something. Amar et al. (2019) also stated that perception is an individuals' competence to see something, and then they explain it into comprehension, attitude, and knowledge. Every individual has the same or different perception from the others. The assumption in individual perception is because that perception is realistic and can understand the object as they are (Démuth, 2013). Perception contains three components: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor (Walgito, 1981); the cognitive component is connected to the experience, opinion, knowledge, and intellectual aspects. The Effective component is connected to the emotional aspect, belief, and feeling. Psychomotor is connected to attitude, motivation, and adaptation. This study focuses on teachers' and students' perceptions in using Microsoft Teams in learning English at SMP Brawijaya Smart School. They give their perception views on attitude, belief, and experience in using Microsoft Teams in learning English. Teachers and students' already experience teaching and learning English using Microsoft Teams during the COVID-19 pandemic.

RESEACH METHODS

This research used a survey design in a quantitative approach. According to Creswell (2012), survey design is quantitative research. The researcher surveys a population or a sample to describe the population's attitude, behaviors, opinions, or characteristics by studying the population sample. The population of this research was 300 students comprised of 8th and 9th grades and 2 English teachers. To decide the sample, the researcher used random sampling. The researcher chose six classes, VIII-C, VIII-D, VIII-E and IX-A, IX-D, IX-D, consisting of 30 students in each class. Thus, there were 180 students and 2 English teachers as the participants of this research. To collect the data, the researcher used a questionnaire to determine the teachers' and students' perceptions from three aspects: the attitude towards Microsoft Teams and its perceived convenience/case of use, the usefulness of Microsoft Teams, and the behavioural intention towards Microsoft Teams. For teachers' questionnaire has 15 statements of 3 aspects, and the students' questionnaire has 20 statements of 3 aspects. The questionnaire was adapted from Binti Mistar & Embi (2016) and Harjanto & Sumarni (2019). The questionnaire used a four-point Likert scale; (1) Strongly Disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Agree, and (4) Strongly Agree. The validity and reliability of data have been processed by using SPSS. All the responses from the questionnaire are collected online through Google Form. Moreover, the questionnaire distributed to the teachers and students was adapted and translated into Bahasa. After collecting the data, the researcher processed the data using SPSS and presented the result in tables.

Research Procedure

In this study, the researcher used six research procedure by Ary et al. (2010) to conduct the research (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Research Procedure by Ary et al., (2010)

The first procedure is planning, the researcher comes with research questions, (1) What are the teachers' perceptions in learning English through Microsoft Teams?, and (2) What are the students' perceptions in learning English through Microsoft Teams?. The second procedure is defining the population, and the researcher decides the population under the study (Ary et al., 2010). In this study, the population is from teachers' and students' at SMP Brawijaya Smart School. The third procedure is sampling. In this study, the researcher used random sampling to decide the sample. The sample in this study is 2 English teachers' and students' from 8th and 9th grade in a total of 180 students'.

The fourth procedure is constructing the instrument. The researcher used a questionnaire adapted from Binti Mistar & Embi (2016) and Harjanto & Sumarni (2019) to collect the data in this study. Then, the fifth procedure is conducting the survey. Since the COVID-19 pandemic, the researcher used Google Form to distribute the questionnaire. Link of Google form sends to the teachers' and students' through personal chat in WhatsApp. The last procedure is processing the data. The researcher used SPSS in analyzing the data.

Data Analysis

There are four steps in analyzing the data, including editing, coding, computerized tests, and tabulation (Sarwono, 2006). Data editing in this research is the researcher checking the collected data. It is expected that there is no misinterpretation of the result in analyzing the data. Coding the data, the researcher gave the code in numbers to the data. The researcher used the Likert scale starting from numbers (1) strongly disagree, (2) disagree, (3) agree, and (4) strongly agree. This process is the purpose of facilitating the calculation of data into software programs such as SPSS. The next is a computerized test. The researcher analyzed the questionnaire through SPSS 25 version to calculate the result. The last is tabulation. After calculating the data through SPSS, the researcher processed the data in a table.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result of Students' Questionnaire

The result of the students' questionnaire about perception using Microsoft Teams to learn English is presented in the Table 1.

Table 1. Students Attitude towards Microsoft Team

No	Indicators	1	2	3	4	Mean Score
1.	Statement 1	3	2	129	46	3.21
2.	Statement 2	0	5	105	29	3.36
3.	Statement 3	1	3	104	72	3.37

4.	Statement 4	0	10	140	30	3.11
5.	Statement 5	1	9	135	35	3.13
6.	Statement 6	1	14	133	32	3.09
7.	Statement 7	0	12	134	34	3.12
8.	Statement 8	0	17	135	28	3.06
9.	Statement 9	3	12	128	37	3.11
10.	Statement 10	1	8	135	36	3.14
11.	Statement 11	0	8	129	43	3.19

Average Mean: 3.20

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree. 3 = Agree and 4 = Strongly Agree

Based on Table 1, the result showed that statement number 3 ($\bar{x} = 3.37$) was ranked highest by mean score was followed consecutively and respectively by statement number 2 ($\bar{x} = 3.36$), statement number 1 ($\bar{x} = 3.21$), statement number 11 ($\bar{x} = 3.19$), statement number 10 ($\bar{x} = 3.14$), statement number 5 ($\bar{x} = 3.13$), statement number 7 ($\bar{x} = 3.12$), statement number 4 and 9 ($\bar{x} = 3.11$), statement number 6 ($\bar{x} = 3.09$) and lastly, statement number 8 ($\bar{x} = 3.08$). It can conclude student's perception of the attitude towards Microsoft Teams and its perceive, convenience/case of use for learning how to use Microsoft Teams was easy is in positive perception with an average mean of 3.20.

Table 2. Students Perception towards The Usefulness of Ms Teams

No	Indicators	1	2	3	4	Mean Score
1.	Statement 12	0	12	138	30	3.10
2.	Statement 13	1	27	124	28	2.99
3.	Statement 14	1	29	126	24	2.96
4.	Statement 15	3	45	110	22	2.84
5.	Statement 16	4	54	104	18	2.76
6.	Statement 17	3	37	126	14	2.84
7.	Statement 18	3	48	107	22	2.82

Average Mean: 2.90

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree. 3 = Agree and 4 = Strongly Agree

Based on Table 2, the result showed that statement number 12 ($\bar{x} = 3.10$) was ranked highest with mean score and was followed consecutively by statement number 13 ($\bar{x} = 2.99$), statement number 14 ($\bar{x} = 2.96$), statement number 15 and 17 ($\bar{x} = 2.84$), statement number 18 ($\bar{x} = 2.82$) and lastly, statement number 16 ($\bar{x} = 2.71$). It can conclude that students' perception of the usefulness of Microsoft Teams for Microsoft Teams is useful for language learning is positive, with an average mean of 2.90.

Table 3. Students Perception on Behavioral Intention towards MS Teams

No	Indicators	1	2	3	4	Mean Score
1.	Statement 19	7	46	112	15	2.75
2.	Statement 20	4	64	100	12	2.67

Average Mean: 2.71

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree. 3 = Agree and 4 = Strongly Agree

Based on Table 3, the result showed that statement number 19 ($\bar{x} = 2.75$) was ranked highest with a mean score and was followed by statement number 20 ($\bar{x} = 2.67$). It can conclude that students'

perception of the behavioral intention towards Microsoft Teams is positive, with an average mean of 2.71.

Result of Teachers' Questionnaire

The result from teachers' questionnaire perception in using Microsoft Teams to learn English is presented in the tables 4.

Table 4. Teachers Attitude towards Microsoft Teams

No	Indicators	1	2	3	4	Mean Score
1.	Statement 1	0	0	1	1	3.50
2.	Statement 2	0	0	0	2	4.00
3.	Statement 3	0	0	0	2	4.00
4.	Statement 4	0	0	1	1	3.50
5.	Statement 5	0	0	0	2	4.00
6.	Statement 6	0	0	0	2	4.00
7.	Statement 7	0	0	1	1	3.50
8.	Statement 8	0	0	1	1	3.50
Average Mean: 3.75						

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree. 3 = Agree and 4 = Strongly Agree

Based on Table 4, the result showed that ranked statement number 2, number 3, number 5, and number 6 ($\bar{x} = 4.00$) were highest with a mean score, followed consecutively by statement number 1, number 4, number 7, and number 8 ($\bar{x} = 3.50$). It can conclude that the Teachers' perception of the attitude towards Microsoft Teams and its perceived convenience/case of use is in positive perception with an average mean of 3.75.

Table 5. Teachers Perception towards The Usefulness of Ms Teams

No	Indicators	1	2	3	4	Mean Score
1.	Statement 9	0	0	0	2	4.00
2.	Statement 10	0	0	1	1	3.50
3.	Statement 11	0	0	1	1	3.50
4.	Statement 12	0	0	0	2	4.00
5.	Statement 13	0	0	0	2	4.00
Average Mean: 3.8						

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree. 3 = Agree and 4 = Strongly Agree

Based on Table 5, the result showed that statement number 9, number 12, and number 13 ($\bar{x} = 4.00$) was ranked highest with mean score and followed statements number 10 and number 11 ($\bar{x} = 3.50$). It can conclude that teachers' perception of the usefulness of Microsoft Teams with Microsoft Teams is helpful for language learning. Using Microsoft Teams saved time in positive perception with an average mean of 3.8.

Table 6. Teachers Perception on Behavioral Intention towards Ms Teams

No	Indicators	1	2	3	4	Mean Score
1.	Statement 14	0	0	1	1	3.50
2.	Statement 15	0	0	1	1	3.50
Average Mean: 3.5						

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Agree and 4 = Strongly Agree

Based on Table 6, the result showed that statement number 14 and number 15 ($\bar{x} = 3.50$) was in the same mean. It can conclude that teachers' perception of Microsoft Teams' behavioral intention is positive with an average mean of 3.5.

Discussion

The result gained from the first aspects revealed teachers' and students' perception of the attitude towards Microsoft Teams and its perceived convenience/case of use was at a positive perception with the highest mean score of teachers' questionnaire $\bar{x} = 4.00$ and students' questionnaire $\bar{x} = 3.37$. It means that teachers and students agreed that the use of Microsoft Teams was easy and convenient for academic purposes. This result is supported by Heath (2019), cited in Duong & Nguyen (2021) Microsoft Teams provides video conferences, discussion boards, and files in one platform, making it easier for teachers and students to use for online learning. The features found in Microsoft Teams are usually on the right side (see figure 2), which starts from activity, chat, teams, assignment, calendar, and files.

Figure 2. Features in Microsoft Teams

The result gained from the second aspect revealed that teachers' and students' perceptions on the usefulness of Microsoft Teams were at a positive perception with the highest mean score of teachers' questionnaire $\bar{x} = 4.00$ and students' questionnaire $\bar{x} = 3.10$. Microsoft Teams as a platform for online learning in SMP Brawijaya Smart School help teachers and students become effective and productive in English online learning. According to Hubbard & Balley (2018), cited in Purba (2021), Microsoft Teams has many practical and effective features that allow understanding. There are seven features in Microsoft Teams for education: activity, chat, teams, assignment, calendar, call, and files, and Microsoft Teams also provided other applications from Microsoft 365. Online English learning at SMP Brawijaya Smart School mostly the teachers and the students used video conference, chats, and assignment features. Figure 3 is one of the learning activities carried out through video conferences and chat features. For video conferences, the teacher usually uses 25 until 30 minutes to explain the material and discuss with students. Within Microsoft Teams, teachers and students can quickly communicate with students, provide virtual meetings, share materials, distribute, and grade assignments.

Figure 3. Video Conference Feature in Microsoft Teams

The result gained from the third aspect revealed that teachers' and students' perceptions of the behavioral intention towards Microsoft Teams were at a positive perception with the highest mean score of teachers' questionnaire \bar{x} = 3.50 and students' questionnaire \bar{x} = 2.71. Both the teachers and students agreed that they would be used Microsoft Teams in their language learning in the future. Microsoft Teams gain knowledge by sharing all information spread faster related to the materials they learned either in person or group or with the teachers through chat room in Microsoft Teams. In line with this, Sheard and Lynch (2003), cited in Binti Mistar & Embi (2016), argue that teaching online can get students' interest because it can reach a flexible education when planned well and respond to the various learning needs.

The result of the teachers' and students' questionnaires from 3 aspects gained the highest average mean score of the attitude towards Microsoft Teams and its perceived, convenient/case of use. The teachers' questionnaire earned a mean score of 3.75, and the students' questionnaire gained a mean score of 3.20. Microsoft Teams was easy to use, can access any time and place, and is convenient for academic engagement purposes. Duong & Nguyen (2021) supported the result that using the platforms in online English learning would give a good attitude to enhance English skills. Figure 4 is an example of students doing a speaking activity with video conference features in Microsoft Teams.

Figure 4. Speaking Activity in Microsoft Teams

CONCLUSION

The result found that Microsoft Teams has a positive perception from teachers and students in English online learning. The highest average mean score gained on the first aspect, the attitude towards Microsoft Teams and its perceived convenience/case of use, with a mean score of teachers' questionnaire \bar{x} = 3.75 and students' questionnaire \bar{x} = 3.20. Teachers' and students' at SMP Brawijaya Smart School found that learning English online through Microsoft Teams was easy and convenient to be used. Microsoft Teams also helped them become more productive in learning English. The use of Microsoft Teams also helped teachers' and students' pass any information discussed quickly. Teachers' and students' at SMP Brawijaya Smart School also found that learning English through Microsoft Teams was a positive idea for having online learning using Microsoft Teams. They felt that Microsoft Teams was also easy to use because Microsoft Teams provided many features that the teachers and students can access in one platform, or we can say that Microsoft Teams is the one-stop platform. Using Microsoft Teams helped them in the English learning process online based on the data. Moreover, this research only provided a positive statement in the questionnaire. It is better if the researcher provides with negative statement too. So, the researcher can find the weaknesses of this platform, not only the strength.

Suggestion

English teachers should make teaching and learning online enjoyable so that the students will not feel bored learning English thrive. So, this platform is suggested for the teachers to teach and learn online for Future researchers since this research focused on teachers' and students' perceptions of using Microsoft Teams to learn English. The researcher expects those future researchers to conduct a similar study involving students' perception of English skills (speaking, writing, reading, and listening). In the questionnaire statement, the future researcher can insert the use of the previous platform before the teachers' and the students' used Microsoft Teams then compare it.

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